

Situated knowledge and the use of generative AI in research software engineering

v1: Draft position paper for the ReSA March 2026 workshop on 'Research Software Engineering in the Age of Generative AI: Building a Community Vision'

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Researcher positionality¹ is important in research, because it influences what questions researchers ask² and what decisions they make during the research process.³ Research software engineers—who combine their expertise in software engineering with research expertise⁴—are no exception to this.

Generative AI systems such as large language models are trained on a vast amount of data: but there is a lack of transparency about what that data is and how representative it is. Earlier AI systems exhibited significant bias in part due to their training data,⁵ and generative AI systems appear to do the same.⁶ Where information about training data exists, it suggests that the data is not representative.⁷ Increasing the usage of generative

¹ This includes aspects of identity and experience such as gender, age, ethnicity, sexuality and socioeconomic status, but also whether someone has power in a particular situation. See Gillian Rose, 'Situating Knowledges: Positionality, Reflexivities and Other Tactics' (1997) 21 *Progress in Human Geography* 305, 308 <<https://doi.org/10.1191/030913297673302122>>.

² The questions asked by researchers are based on (often implicit) understandings of the world, and the knowledge produced as a result reflects this. See Vivien Burr, *Social Constructionism* (2nd edn, Routledge 2003) ch 8.

³ Of course, some researchers have more power than others over decision-making in the research process. For more on researcher power in knowledge production, see Joey Sprague, *Feminist Methodologies for Critical Researchers: Bridging Differences* (AltaMira Press 2005) 54–66.

⁴ About | Society of Research Software Engineering' (*Society of Research Software Engineering*) <<https://society-rse.org/about/>>

⁵ This has been extensively documented. Some of the most famous examples include: Joy Buolamwini and Timnit Gebru, 'Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification' *Proceedings of the 1st Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency* (PMLR 2018) <<https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a.html>> accessed 4 March 2026; Virginia Eubanks, *Automating Inequality: How High-Tech Tools Profile, Police, and Punish the Poor* (St Martin's Press 2018); Catherine D'Ignazio and Lauren F Klein, *Data Feminism* (MIT Press 2020).

⁶ See for example Isobel Barry and Elise Stephenson, 'The Gendered, Epistemic Injustices of Generative AI' *Australian Feminist Studies* 1 <<https://doi.org/10.1080/08164649.2025.2480927>>.

⁷ The developers of commercially available large language models have not made information about their training data publicly available. AI systems are known to have been trained on existing publicly available data sets, many of which have been shown to be biased. See for example Kate

AI increases the extent to which these biased and unbalanced systems are used in the process of research—including in the development and application of research questions—with consequences for the knowledge produced as a result.

Over time, across different research domains, research progress has increasingly benefited from the input of researchers with different viewpoints, experiences, and expertise.⁸ Challenging the fallacy of the single 'objective' observer,⁹ researcher diversity leverages the experiences and values of a wide range of scientists to increase the rigour of research and strengthen its conclusions.¹⁰ When considering the potential impact of research, explicitly including researchers with particular standpoints that put them closer to the issues being examined can strengthen this impact.¹¹ Where the research relates to people, this can be done through a shift from research as something that is done to people,¹² to collaborative, participatory,¹³ and community-based knowledge-making.

Increased reliance on generative AI in research—including in research software engineering—however, reverses this trend. Ceding some or all of the development of research software to large language models loses this diversity of viewpoints, experiences, expertise and values, which enrich the decisions made on how to conduct research and thus the knowledge produced. Instead, LLMs present a single, 'flattened' standpoint which reflects the biases of the data on which it was trained. Instead of a multiplicity of voices, ideas and challenges to existing assumptions related to research software, LLM-facilitated research risks perpetuating the values and assumptions of those who already hold power in the research process.

Crawford, *Atlas of AI: Power, Politics, and the Planetary Costs of Artificial Intelligence* (Yale University Press 2021) chs 3–4.

⁸ See for example Michael El Boghdady, 'Equality and Diversity in Research: Building an Inclusive Future' (2025) 18 *BMC Research Notes* 14 <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-025-07096-4>>; Magda Titirici and others, 'Global Perspectives on the Critical Role of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Science' (2025) 6 *Cell Reports Physical Science* 102791 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2025.102791>>.

⁹ The idea that a scientific observer could be impartial and unbiased emerged in 17th century London around the Royal Society. See John Law, 'STS as Method' in Ulrike Felt and others (eds), *The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies* (4th edn, The MIT Press 2017) 36.

¹⁰ This epistemological approach is termed 'feminist empiricism.' See Britta Wigginton and Michelle N Lafrance, 'Learning Critical Feminist Research: A Brief Introduction to Feminist Epistemologies and Methodologies' [2019] *Feminism & Psychology* <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0959353519866058>> accessed 23 November 2021.

¹¹ This is particularly true when the impact is social. For more on this, see bell hooks, *Feminist Theory from Margin to Center* (South End Press 1984).

¹² Even well-intentioned research about people can fall into the trap of cementing problematic power relationships, especially when those people are already marginalised. See Linda Alcoff, 'The Problem of Speaking for Others' [1991] *Cultural Critique* 5 <<https://doi.org/10.2307/1354221>>

¹³ 'Participation' can mean different things in different contexts: from giving input (which may or may not be taken), to token inclusion, to full control. See Sherry R Arnstein, 'A Ladder Of Citizen Participation' (1969) 35 *Journal of the American Institute of Planners* 216 <<https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>>.